

SOCIOECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF WASTELANDS WITH THE HELP OF HYDROPONICS FARMING

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: Today, the world is facing many issues like the inefficient economy, social deprivation, and deterioration of the environment. In India, these problems were further enhanced by a rapidly growing population that also questioned food security. Furthermore, traditional agriculture faces many problems like climate change and soil-borne diseases.

Design/Methodology: Compared to conventional agriculture, a hydroponic system provides a sterile environment for farming. Moreover, the Government can use wasteland for crop production through hydroponic (soilless) farming. That may help the Indian Government to boost the country's economy because land is an essential asset of every country.

Findings: Hydroponic systems are commended for producing more crop variety because they do not need soil, which yields more than four times in a similar soil area.

Practical Implications: The increase in crop yield by hydroponic farming compared to conventional agriculture methods can fulfill the growing population's food demand.

Originality/value: Hydroponic farming may contribute to India's socioeconomic development by providing income from wasteland. Therefore, by creating jobs, hydroponic farming may significantly contribute to the growth of the nation's economy.

Keywords: Climate change, Hydroponics, Land development, Monetization, Soilless farming

Paper Type: Review Article

1. INTRODUCTION

India is a developing nation that is going through a period of environmental degradation, social squalor, and an inefficient economy. These problems are further enhanced by the rapidly growing population (Ellis et al. 2013; Steffen et al. 2011, 2015; Halarnkar 2015; Kumar et al., 2020). The rise in the population also increased the demand for food, which may be expected to enhance up to 59% to 98% by 2050 in India. An increase in demand for food also exerts pressure on the economy, which creates a wide gap between consumers and available supplies, which results in scarcities and shortages. To address these issues, the Indian Government has stated that it intends to expand its economy by \$81 billion (€68.5 billion) by monetizing government-owned assets such as land, highways, and stadiums (Rai 2021). A large area of India presently has wasteland (land that has become barren or overgrown) (Wasteland Atlas of India 2019), which can be used for monetization in the current program of India, such as for developing airports, railway stations, industrial space, etc. (Tirumala and Tiwari 2021). One method to develop wasteland areas is a hydroponic farming system that can be done in collaboration with the local farmer. In addition, India has just 30,000 hectares (ha) of polyhouse constructions (also known as a 'hoop house') or covered farming. Thus, the Indian Government can develop a wasteland for economic growth. The recent Government of India's schemes and programs has focused on the sustainability approach.

According to Sisodia et al. (2020), Hydroponics is a contemporary farming method that offers a sustainable environment for plants to flourish without soil. It can be set up in any place because it does not require soil, and we need a plastic infrastructure, nutrients, energy, and skilled labor. So, for hydroponic farming, any place can be used, like barren or unutilized land. To feed the growing population, middle-income countries like India must accelerate their agricultural output (Hallikainen 2019). As a result, we can use hydroponic farming to develop India's wasteland area. Due to the controlled environmental conditions, hydroponic farming is also more secure than traditional farming since climatic variations can be balanced inside the systems without compromising the output of crops (Pomoni et al. 2023). In the past 60 years, the agricultural trade has grown ten times, and this trend is predicted to continue (Stevanovi et al. 2016). Consequently, it mainly has an impact on the ecology and climate which effect the productivity in traditional agriculture system (Schmitz et al. 2012). While in hydroponic systems crops can be grown throughout the year which further boosts annual yield (Kumar et al. 2020; Rajiv and Kumari 2023). The productivity of plants grown in hydroponic systems is 2–5 times higher than that of traditional agriculture systems, according to UN statistics on the state of the world's population (Mehra 2021). As a result, the hydroponic system may be advantageous in India and promote sustainability and food security (Pinstrup-Andersen 2018).

In addition, the Indian Government has launched several support programs under Start-up India, such as the Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojna, MSME, etc., that can be used to finance investments in companies that will improve the country's food security. Additionally, local food production promotes greater employability in the industry and a rise in demand within the region. Every community and country aspires to be self-sufficient. Narendra Modi,

the prime minister of India, started the self-Reliant India Campaign to boost the nation's economy in the face of the coronavirus outbreak. Residents of that area will have access to freshly grown crops if hydroponic farming is successful in wastelands.

Further, higher commitment to agriculture activities also confirms a significant increase in employability. An increase in per capita income would lead to the country's economic growth and put forth a positive impact on ecological security, economic efficiency, and social equity. Thus, hydroponic farming can have environmental, economic, and social implications. This paper will deal with the wasteland area and land monetization policy of India and hydroponic farming and explore the horticultural tool for wasteland development. This article's goal is to provide readers with a general understanding of how India's wasteland region might be utilized to boost economic development and supply the nation's expanding population with food. Therefore, the socioeconomic development of wasteland through hydroponic farming would be the main topic of this review.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Wasteland Cover in India

The ever-increasing population contributes to environmental damages, primarily through the reduction of soil cover and consequent flooding. Due to human activities, global damage to soil is also noticed (Dazzi et al. 2019). Wasteland is a degraded area of land that, with moderate effort, might be covered in vegetation, is now underutilized, and is degrading due to improper water and soil management or natural reasons. According to the Wasteland Map of India (Wasteland Atlas of India 2019) (Fig. 1), the total area of wastelands in the nation was projected to be 5,57,66.51 sq. Kms comprised 16.96% of the Total Geographical Area (TGA) in 2015–16. However, as a matter of fact, about 40 percent of our 1.3 billion population depends on this wasteland for livelihood (DOLR 2016). Due to this, the Government formed a National Wastelands Development Board (NWDB) under the Ministry of Environment and Forests to develop these wastelands. Its purpose was to treat all commons as wasteland and develop it for agriculture, infrastructures such as roads, or industry. The NWDB's mission is unambiguous, and its outcome is to see land merely in terms of what can be extracted from it. One of the recent initiatives by the Government of India is the [Green India Mission \(NITI Aayog, 2021\)](#). The aim is to fight climate change by increasing the forest cover of India by 5 million hectares. The Indian Government can use the technique of hydroponic farming for the development of wasteland under the Green India Mission.

2.2 Land Monetization Policy in India

The land is the natural resource of every country and a significant component of a country's socioeconomic and ecological health, acting as a foundation for infrastructure development (Rathee 2014; Tirumala and Tiwari 2021). The management of environmental resources, national food security, and quality of life are all significantly impacted by land use (Rathee 2014). One of the most practical choices for both the state and federal governments, i.e., to monetize land, is to raise the much-needed funds for upgrading or developing the necessary infrastructure. The Government has restricted land resources due to this sustainable use, and management of land resources is a necessity for the welfare of the people. Wasteland areas

The importance of ensuring appropriate land use held by the Central and State governments and Public Sector Undertakings is underlined by the 13th Finance Commission of India. The Finance Commission of India claims that underutilized premium lands have a significant potential for increasing revenue.

On the one hand, monetizing these wasteland assets may serve as important funding sources for the corresponding Public Sector Undertakings, Railways, Airports, Port Trusts, municipal corporations, etc. If designed for commercial use, a prosperous land monetization process should be financially viable and produce enough income for the project's stockholders. Over the past few years, the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) model has become a viable choice for growth. It integrates the public and government sectors with market efficiency, professionalism, and private sector knowledge (NITI Aayog 2021). One such use may be hydroponic farming, which utilizes these lands; it can provide employment, food security, and a clean environment by adding more plants to the earth's surface. The aforementioned measures would increase the number of jobs created in the area both during and after the hydroponic farming process, give the expanding population the food security they so desperately need, and improve the area's economic standing and standard of living. The lengthy and complicated process of acquiring the necessary permits from different civic authorities has prevented much progress from being made on the monetization front, despite the significant availability of land banks with Central and state government agencies. More must be done to accelerate the monetization process to create an Atmnirbhar Bharat, even though several steps have already been launched at the federal and state levels to speed up the existing process.

2.3 Concept of Hydroponics

Hydroponics farming is a system that offers a suitable atmosphere for plants to grow without soil using mineral nutrient solutions (Dos Santos et al. 2013; Sisodia et al. 2020; Mint 2021). In theory, the word "hydroponics" was derived from the Greek words 'hydro' which means water, and 'ponos' which means labor, and exactly means water work means growing plants in water (Sharma et al. 2018). It is a form of "precision farming" where nothing is wasted. The roots are submerged in nutrient solutions with pH-balanced and need to be changed after some time. This excludes the plants' daily watering, and pH-balanced nutrient solutions result in nutrient-rich crop-producing better yields. Hydroponic farming is safer than traditional agriculture due to the controlled setup. It may be used for small-scale production like terrace farming to large-scale productions like unutilized land (wasteland). Population increase, climate change, land degradation, water shortages, and food security were identified as the most pressing challenges of the previous ten years by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030 (Abusin and Mandikiana 2020). According to the Brundtland Commission Report from 1987 (Brundtland, G.H., 1987), development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs is the notion of sustainable development. Thus, Hydroponics is considered as a promising remedy for the rising worry about food security in the upcoming years. The hydroponic system in India could be advantageous and promote sustainability and food security. All these can be achieved using hydroponic farming, a sustainable solution with

good potential. From the early studies of Jones (1982), Jensen (1997), and Hershey (1994) to more recent works by Schnitzler (2012), Sharma et al. (2018), and Sihombing et al. (2018), Hydroponics has been found to be one of the good alternatives to traditional agriculture methods.

Material pertaining to the hydroponic system:

The essential requirement for the hydroponic system is as follow:

Hydroponic production function

$HP=f(\text{Water, Nutrients, Root Support, EC; LC})$

Where; HP= Hydroponic production, EC=energy cost; LC= labor cost

2.3.1 Water

Plants need water with a pH level of around 6–6.5.

2.3.2 Nutrients

The plant requires many nutrients for its growth, which are categorized into two classes, macronutrients, and micronutrients, which are directly absorbed by plants through the nutrient solution in a hydroponic system; due to this, plants have a higher growth rate than soil. The ideal nutritional composition includes macronutrients like nitrogen, potassium, magnesium, calcium, sulfur, and phosphorus and micronutrients like iron, copper, manganese, zinc, molybdenum, and boron.

2.3.3 Root Support.

Although the plant does not need soil in the hydroponic system, but plant's roots need something to hold on to. This includes materials like vermiculite, perlite, peat moss, coconut fiber, and rock wool.

2.3.4 Energy Cost

According to Barbosa et al. (2015), a hydroponics system consumes a lot of energy. The overall value of hydroponics goods declined as energy consumption grew in a system where there is a negative connection between income and energy use costs. The plant needs light for the process of photosynthesis that makes food. The requirement of light is different for each plant and can be maintained by the placement of lights. In a hydroponic system, we must either provide room between the plant's base and the water reservoir or use an air pump to oxygenate the container.

2.3.5 Labor Cost

In economics, labor is a vital component of production. Wages are the payment for labor. Similar research on tomatoes in Nigeria found that labor had a major impact on productivity

(Umar and Abdulkadir 2015). The findings showed that a 1% increase in labor costs would result in a 1.16 % rise in the value of hydroponics goods.

2.4 Types of Hydroponic Systems

A hydroponic system can be set up in a variety of ways, but the fundamental components always remain the same. There are primarily six categories in which hydroponic systems can be used. Table 1 gives a comprehensive and thorough look at the six types of hydroponic systems, making it easier to determine which system is suitable for them (Fig. 2).

Table 1: Different type of hydroponic systems, their advantage and disadvantage

SN.	Type of Hydroponic System	Principle	Advantage	Disadvantage
1.	The Wick System	<p>The wick's capillary action carries the nutrient solution to the plant roots once it is pushed from the reservoir up the growth tray.</p> <p>The wick system operates automatically. There are no moving components or pumps used in it (Fig. 2 a).</p>	<p>Very simple to set up.</p> <p>Excellent starting point for beginners and children.</p>	<p>Insufficient for bigger plants.</p> <p>Nutrient usage could be more efficient.</p>
2.	Deep Water Culture (DWC) System	In a net pot suspended above a reservoir of nutrients and water, plants are kept nourished by a floating platform. Plant roots are stretched and suspended in the oxygenated, nutrient-rich fluid (Fig. 2 b).	<p>Inexpensive.</p> <p>Simple to set up.</p> <p>Recirculating.</p> <p>Water-saving.</p>	<p>Inadequate for bigger plants.</p> <p>Unsuitable for plants with a lengthy growth season.</p>
3.	Ebb and Flow System (Flood and Drain)	They are sometimes referred to as Flood & Drain. The device streams the nutritional solution onto the grow tray, surrounding the plant roots, and drains it back. A timer-connected pump is frequently used to automate it (Fig. 2 c).	<p>Appropriate for plants that need water.</p> <p>Simple to set up.</p>	<p>Pump/timer failure and power outages are possible.</p> <p>Demand plenty of growth media. Thus, the necessity for appropriate expertise.</p>
4.	Nutrient Film Technique (N.F.T)	A pump continually propels the nutritional solution onto the grow tray, which flows over the plants. It subsequently drains down the slightly lower canal back to the reservoir. No need for a timer (Fig. 2 d).	<p>Use of the growth media was minimal.</p> <p>Recirculating.</p> <p>Water-saving.</p>	<p>Vulnerable to power interruptions and pump failure.</p> <p>Not appropriate for big, heavy plants.</p>
5.	Drip System	The drip system uses a network of drip lines to pump the nutrient solution down the tube and drop it	Easily constructed and operated.	Variations in pH and nutrition.

		onto the roots of the plants. A timer is frequently used to perform the procedure automatically (Fig. 2 e).	Enhanced nutrition and water schedule control.	Ideally suited to larger gardens.
6.	Aeroponics	Plant roots are continually misted with the nutritional solution while suspended in the air. The misting interval is rather brief and is carried out by a pump that is timed (Fig. 2 f).	The roots of plants have access to plenty of oxygen. Use of the growth media was minimal. Effective use of water.	More costly than other kinds. More susceptible to the drying effects of power outages.

Figure 2: Diagrammatic representation of six types of hydroponic systems (a) The Wick

System, (b) the Deep Water Culture (DWC) System, (c) the Ebb and Flow System (Flood and Drain), (d) the Nutrient Film Technique (NFT), (e) Drip System and (f) Aeroponics

2.5 Plant Suitable for hydroponics farming in the Indian environment

We can grow practically everything with hydroponic systems, albeit certain veggies do better than others. However, many plants are simple to cultivate, including lettuce, cucumber, tomato, capsicum, peppers, kale, spinach, beans, peppers, capsicum radish, ginger, and peppermint.

2.6 Advantages of Hydroponics

Hydroponic farming provides 50% faster than traditional farming due to constant and readily available nutrition. Secondly, fresh crops can be harvested from a hydroponic system for the whole year. The most significant advantage of hydroponic farming over conventional farming is the absence of the need for pesticides and herbicides. Hydroponic farming does not waste any water since it stays in the system and may be utilized again, lessening the requirement for a steady freshwater supply.

3. METHODOLOGY

We selected lettuce as an example plant in this review and provided data from cost-benefit analyses of traditional and hydroponic farming. Lettuce is a well-known crop that is widely utilized as a daily vegetable in a variety of meals. The themes chosen for the information gathering were hydroponics, traditional agriculture, and greenhouses. 16% of the works utilized and cited in this work were published between 1982 and 2011, 37% between 2012 and 2017, and 50% between 2018 and the present, according to the evaluated resources.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Economic Consideration

The wasteland development by hydroponic farming can provide many opportunities to the local people, the private sector, and lastly Indian Government. All the economic benefits are discussed in this section, like Cost and Benefit Analysis, human capital formation, revenue potential, etc.,

4.2 Cost and Benefit Analysis (CBA)

A cost-benefit analysis is a "method used to quantify the advantages of making a choice or acting, less the expenses involved in doing. It may be characterized as a process for calculating all expenses related to and potential earnings from a business opportunity or proposal. Examining the value for money for a specific project or investment opportunity considers both quantitative and qualitative aspects. The opportunity costs of the investment in the project to incur the expenditures are also taken into consideration by the majority of economists. The present paper calculated the CBA for hydroponically grown lettuce in India.

In terms of yield per area, the hydroponic production of lettuce in India will be as follow:

Number of plants per Acre=26000 (Barbosa et al. 2015)

1 hectare = 2.47 acre

Cost of one acre hydroponic farming = Rs. 1.10 Cr approximately

So, the cost of one hectare= 1.10*2.47= 2.717 Cr

1 hectare= 10000 m²

Yield of lettuce per m²=41 ± 6.1 kg/m²/y (Barbosa et al. 2015)

Yield of plant per hectare=41*10000=410000 kg/h/y

One kg of lettuce cost = Rs. 200 / kg at Indian Market in 2021.

Total value of lettuce for one year= $200 \times 410000 = \text{Rs. } 8,20,00000 = 8.2 \text{ Cr}$

The CAB analysis can be done by subtracting the costs of the project from the number of total project benefits associated with the project decision.

Profit per hectare per year= $8.2 - 2.717 = 5.483 \text{ Cr}$

By estimating CAB analysis, we can see that hydroponic farming has a profit of 5.483 Cr, making it a boon for the wasteland or any unutilized area (Fig. 3). Thus, we can say that hydroponic farming is a very lucrative project to be carried out. The results of Barbosa et al. (2015) showed that Hydroponics grown lettuce plants have 11 ± 1.7 times higher yields than conventionally grown lettuce. Bangladesh also enjoys a competitive advantage in the production of mustard-based, onion-based, and lentil-based products (Anjum and Barmon 2018; Tithi and Barmon 2018). No matter what kind of structure they are utilized in, hydroponic systems are 60% more lucrative (Rajiv and Kumari 2023). Many nations enjoy a competitive advantage in the production of certain commodities (Abusin and Mandikiana 2020). Thus, we can say that it will also help the Indian Government in generating potential revenue.

Figure 3: Cost and Benefit Analysis (CBA) in percentage for lettuce plant in a hydroponic system.

4.3 Human Capital Formation

It is the process of obtaining and growing the population of individuals with the knowledge, training, and experience necessary for a nation's political and economic progress. Additionally, it will promote economic growth and development and quickly expand jobs. Human capital and economic expansion are related in a cause-and-effect manner. It has a significant effect on hydroponics productivity. Human capital formation will play an essential role in hydroponics farming as countries like Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and Israel hire skilled workers for farming and provide training for that. The Indian Government should also focus on forming human capital for hydroponic farming to combat food security. A positive

relationship indicated that productivity and revenue in Hydroponics increased significantly when labor in Hydroponics increased (Malik et al. 2019).

4.4 Monetization

Monetization (also spelled monetization) is the process of converting something into legal tender money. The Indian Government has stated that it plans to monetize government-owned assets such as land, highways, and stadiums in order to collect \$81 billion (€68.5 billion). Under the National Monetization Pipeline (NMP) initiative, it plans to complete this in four years, from 2022 to 2025. By transferring the revenue rights, the primary goal is to unleash the value of brownfield projects and attract players from the private sector. Using wasteland for hydroponic farming brings the private sector and Government together, and it also helps generate money through crop production. This will result in employment generation in the region during and after hydroponic farming, provide much-needed food security to the growing population, and improve the region's economic profile and quality of life.

4.5 Revenue Potential

India's economy would benefit if lettuce were produced there today since it might be 30% less expensive than imported lettuce. Barbosa et al. (2015) showed that lettuce plants have 11 times higher yields in hydroponic farming than in conventional farming. Growing lettuce with the help of hydroponic farming provides a profit per hectare per year of about 5.483 Cr in the wasteland area. In a similar vein, imported cherry tomatoes might cost Rs 1,000 per kilogram, but domestically grown cherry tomatoes may only cost Rs 200. Additionally, according to research by the National Restaurant Association of India and Technopak, an Indian food services company, the market for vegetables is currently worth \$48 billion and is expected to reach \$78 billion in five years. While wealthy nations produce more than 40 tons/ha of vegetables, the average output in India is only 17 tons/ha. This poses a worrisome picture as India's projected demand for vegetables by 2050 is 350 million tonnes (Kanwar 2016). To meet this projected demand for vegetable production, hydroponic farming is very suitable for farmers. Moreover, India's market of Hydroponics is likely to grow at a CAGR of 13.53% between 2021 and 2028 (DataM Intelligence 2019). So, we can say that the development of wasteland using hydroponic farming may have the potential to generate revenue for the Indian Government.

4.6 Social Aspects

The wasteland development by hydroponic farming will benefit local communities, which usually involve intensive profit-oriented projects by government and private bodies. Hydroponics strongly influences rural communities by reducing rural migration, strengthening farmer business models, increasing agritourism, improving local economies and infrastructure, and, finally, training farmers' abilities for more efficient agricultural techniques (Pomoni et al. 2023). Besides this, it provides fresh fruits and vegetables.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Governments are expanding sustainable approaches to cope with global warming and climate change issues worldwide. The Indian Government is also working on various policies like the

monetization of lands for the development of public-private partnership provisions. The Indian Government may also implement the policy plan that would provide the finest long-term conditions for both public-private partnerships. The funders could be interested in building hydroponic farms in barren places, such as deserts, mountainous terrain, and remote locations, where traditional agriculture may be difficult. According to hydroponic system theories, the system is capable of producing a sufficient quantity of food to satisfy local needs without relying on climatic factors, imports, soil quality, or other factors. Over traditional farming methods, Hydroponics is becoming more and more popular, especially on underutilized land that can only sustain a small amount of production. In the end, we may conclude that the Indian Government should prioritize the development of hydroponic farming in wasteland areas since this would eventually affect economic growth. It can fulfill several objectives, such as it can (i) increasing greenery, (ii) enhancing crop production, (iii) providing employability, and lastly (iv) generating revenue. Thus, hydroponic farming may act as a first step towards a self-reliant India.

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